

1 Convivial Heritage: A Disruptive Archaeology of 2 Species Coexistence

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9
10 Abstract:

11 **This paper explores the utility of conviviality thinking for archaeological theory and practice. It**
12 **first situates calls for convivial analysis as a response to the excesses of late capitalism and the**
13 **existential challenges of the global Anthropocene polycrisis. The paper then highlights the critical,**
14 **ethical, and interpretive potentials of the concept to re-think human-animal coexistence, to frame**
15 **new approaches to ecological conservation, and to creatively re-imagine shared multispecies**
16 **futures. A suite of examples from hunter-gatherer archaeology and archaeological museums is**
17 **offered to illustrate how conviviality thinking helps to challenge traditional representations of the**
18 **past and contributes to an engaged, post-critical approach to museum and heritage practices**
19 **fostering fruitful dialogue on the diversity of species co-living. Conviviality constitutes a powerful**
20 **lens to integrate theory and practice and to draw on the empirical strengths of archaeology while**
21 **recognizing the need to speak to a critical moment in planetary history.**

22
23 **Keywords:** deep history; multispecies archaeology; Anthropocene heritage; post-critical museum;
24 conviviality; species co-living; conservation; archaeological imagination

25 26 **Introduction**

27 The COVID-19 pandemic has resurged both academic and public attention as to how we come to live
28 together with nonhuman animals (Searle and Turnbull, 2020). There is a growing recognition that
29 elevated risk for potentially devastating zoonoses may become the new *status quo* in the multi-crisis
30 that is the ‘Anthropocene’ (Gibson et al., 2015; Horn and Bergthaller, 2022; Morin and Kern, 1999). A
31 key diagnosis is that the fulmination of zoonotic disease vividly illustrates some of the many pathologies
32 of present-day modes of human-animal cohabitation, most of which are inextricably tied to the pervasive
33 extractive logic of capitalist systems and the alienation and commodification of nature they promote

34 (Cassegård, 2021). Although engagement with the Anthropocene has provoked diverse, sometimes
35 conflicting responses, there is a broad emerging consensus that the planetary futures alarmingly put at
36 stake by current human Earth-system involvement cannot be safeguarded by working *against* or *above*
37 nonhuman nature, but instead call for new ways of *working with* the many nonhumans we share the
38 planet with (e.g., Horn and Bergthaller, 2022; Schroer, 2022). Haraway (2016) has famously urged for
39 the critical need to ‘make [new] kin’ (see also Van Horn et al., 2021) and to acknowledge the
40 interdependencies of species that are the foundation of shared planetary livelihoods. Cultivating the
41 latter is now increasingly argued to require new forms of interspecies attentiveness, care and
42 responsibility (Kirksey, 2014; Tsing et al., 2020; van Dooren et al., 2016). The Anthropocene moment
43 can so be understood as a critical inflection point challenging long-held assumptions on the limits and
44 preconditions of earthly *habitability* (Fleetwood, 2023) – how we, as humans, can sustainably and
45 ethically inhabit the planet. Importantly, however, this question cannot be addressed from an exclusively
46 human-centered perspective but demands multispecies sensibilities. Futurity debates cannot evade
47 questions of nonhuman life. Understanding the matrix of human-animal co-dependency and affirming
48 the inescapability of attending to, enabling, and cultivating multispecies neighborhoods consequently
49 emerge as central priorities of future-oriented research.

50 Devising new ways of living together with other animals rooted in awareness and constructive
51 recognition of their projects, needs and perspectives has been framed as a question of ‘conviviality’
52 (e.g., Donati, 2019; Hinchliffe and Whatmore, 2006; Rigby, 2018), and to foster truly convivial forms
53 of multispecies life is regarded to be a key to successfully navigating the deep futures that lie ahead.
54 Conviviality studies thereby join forces, and continue to be informed by, broader concerns in
55 multispecies studies and the environmental humanities, habitability studies, coexistence studies (Pooley
56 et al., 2021; Schroer, 2021), conservation science (Büscher and Fletcher, 2020; Massarella et al., 2023),
57 security studies (El Kateb et al., 2015), and the emergent systems view of life (Capra and Luisi, 2014).
58 Given this upsurge of interest in convivial species co-living, it is surprising how little attention the issue
59 has so far garnered in archaeology and heritage studies, and this even though these disciplines can
60 arguably contribute unique and critical insights and perspectives to broader discussions on the situated

61 dynamics of human-animal cohabitation (Armstrong Oma, 2018; Hamilakis and Overton, 2013; Kost
62 and Hussain, 2019; Stobiecka, 2022a).

63 We here argue that conviviality indeed provides an hitherto overlooked lens to open up an
64 entirely novel domain of archaeological inquiry and knowledge production, helping to propel the field
65 from a narrow engagement with ‘matters of fact’ to wider-ranging ‘matters of concern’ (cf. Horn and
66 Bergthaller, 2022: 15; Latour, 2004). A concern with convivial forms of multispecies life coevally
67 retables questions on how to portray and interrogate the past in museum spaces. By engaging with these
68 and related issues, the paper ultimately probes into some of the prospects of post-critical (Anker and
69 Felski, 2017; Di Leo, 2014; Röder, 2014) and post-qualitative inquiry (Lather and St. Pierre, 2013; St.
70 Pierre, 2021) for archaeology and interdisciplinary museum studies writ large. We first distill a general
71 concept of multispecies conviviality based on a focused review of the literature. We then re-read deep-
72 time instances of human-animal cohabitation through a conviviality lens and consider the responsibility
73 of archaeology to bring such perspectives to public attention. We draw on examples from deep-time
74 archaeology because the deep past is a ‘foreign country’ (Lowenthal, 2015) and likely frames an archive
75 of non-analogue, strictly alternative modes of species co-living. Following this refurbishment of
76 archaeological inquiry, we offer an archaeology of conviviality as a promising and urgently needed
77 intervention within future-oriented discussions of planetary livelihoods.

78

79 **From Human Conviviality to Multispecies Conviviality**

80 The notion of conviviality was introduced to the Western scholarly corpus by the Austrian philosopher
81 and social critic Ivan Illich. Illich was an adamant commentator of institutionalized modernity in the
82 industrial post-war West and in his widely-celebrated *Tools for Conviviality* (2009 [1973]) coined
83 conviviality as an ideal to combat the degrading effects of capitalism. Following Illich (2009: 18),
84 conviviality has to be understood in opposition to (capitalist) industrial productivity. Whereas in
85 capitalist regimes workers are alienated from their products, conviviality was offered to describe and
86 foster “*autonomous* and *creative* intercourse among persons, and the intercourse of persons with their
87 environment [...] in contrast with the conditioned response of persons to the demands made upon them
88 by others, and by a man-made environment” (Illich, 2009: 19, emphasis added). For Illich (2009: 19),

89 conviviality therefore conveyed the aspiration for “individual freedom realized in personal
90 interdependence”, thus having “intrinsic ethical value.” As Krauss (2021) points out, Illich’s account is
91 premised on justice and freedom in responsible interdependence, with the hope to engender a ‘convival
92 society’ founded upon “knowledge and tools not serving individualized profit and industrialized
93 production, but the common good, while limiting resource consumption for the rich.” Conviviality, in
94 this context, already implies the idea of a ‘commons’ (Ostrom, 1990) – it helps to both cultivate and
95 perpetuate it – yet ‘commoning’ is primarily understood as an intra-human process that highlights
96 participatory, distributed and bottom-up society-making.

97 Illich’s (2009 [1973]) timeless reaction to the negative and future-threatening trends that run
98 through contemporary societies and his thorough critique of capitalism and consumerism became a
99 referential point for the conviviality movement, a group of French intellectuals who in two manifestos
100 called for convivialism as a regulative idea for alternative forms of collaborative, joyful post-growth
101 social cohabitation (The Convivialist Manifesto, 2014; The Second Convivialist Manifesto, 2020).
102 These authors offer an understanding of convivialism as “a mode of living together (*con-vivere*) that
103 values human relationships and cooperation and enables us to challenge one another without resorting
104 to mutual slaughter and in a way that ensures consideration for others and for nature” (The Convivialist
105 Manifesto, 2014: 25), practicable for example through grassroots movements, participatory
106 collaboratives and ‘slow’ trends. Convivialism advocates new forms of life based on ideas of a common
107 humanity, common sociality, individuation and managed conflict. The point is not to seek social
108 harmony and the absence of conflict but to foster a sense of cohesion and sharedness that rests on a
109 delicate balance between sameness and difference. Conviviality in this sense resides in the capacity of
110 individuals to generatively interact with one another on their own accord and on their own terms, while
111 nonetheless satisfying their possibly divergent needs and agendas.

112 In the foreword to the first conviviality manifesto, Adloff (2014: 10) sharp-sightedly notes that
113 the basis for this way of re-thinking social life is an updated reading of Marcel Mauss’ landmark study
114 *The Gift* (2011 [1925]). The idea, resonating with much contemporary scholarship on sociality and co-
115 sociality, is that any meaningful social relationship is underwritten by some form of reciprocity, even if
116 it is ‘unbalanced’. The French convivialists thereby extend the Maussian notion of gift exchange as a

117 society-making obligate practice to include the natural world, maintaining that “the gift/counter-gift
118 relationship, and the relationship of interdependence, must [also] be applied to [nonhuman] animals –
119 which must no longer be thought of as fodder for industry – and to the earth in general” (The Convivialist
120 Manifesto, 2014: 33). Significantly, and writing in the current atmosphere of catastrophe and the long
121 shadow of the Anthropocene, they accordingly identify conviviality with animals as a key condition for
122 a good, just, and sustainable life on Earth.

123 The resulting vision of equity, the basis for conviviality, must then encompass “the animal world
124 in the name of anti-speciesism and common naturalness” (The Second Convivialist Manifesto, 2020).
125 This understanding not only reverberates with the understanding of conviviality in the English academic
126 discourse as a form of living together across difference and diversity (Heil, 2020; Samanani, 2023) –
127 sometimes celebrated as the ‘convivial turn’ in cultural and postcolonial studies (e.g., Gidley, 2013;
128 Lapiņa, 2016; Neal et al., 2019) – it coevally takes up recent generalizations of gift-exchange as a
129 constitutive and regulatory dynamic of generative interspecies relationships in archaeology and cultural
130 anthropology (Hussain et al., 2022; Hussain and Floss, 2015; Nadasdy, 2007). Stuart Hall’s (1993: 361)
131 incisive declaration that the capacity to “live with difference” likely delineates “the coming question of
132 the twenty-first century” – in the light of pressing Anthropocene challenges – then calls for capacities,
133 concepts and imaginaries to ‘live with other species’ in the near and long-term future. Historical and
134 future-oriented analyses of conviviality here promise to help formulate and identify affirmative,
135 constructive models for thinking and living otherwise in more-than-human worlds. As Gilroy (2004)
136 insists, the development of convivial cultures based on the perpetual negotiation of other-directed
137 hospitality in the face of overwhelming prejudice-driven hostility must rank among the big, overriding
138 ambitions and destinator projects of our time.

139 When contextualized and understood in this way, it is not surprising that considerations of
140 conviviality have recently surfaced in the ecological literature on ecosystem conservation and restoration
141 (Büscher and Fletcher, 2020; Massarella et al., 2022, 2023). Conviviality there is framed as the “building
142 of long-lasting, engaging and open-ended relationships with nonhumans and ecologies” (Büscher and
143 Fletcher, 2019: 286) which has given voice to the ‘convivial conservation’ proposal as a radical
144 antithesis to the dominant Western and human-centered alternatives. Conviviality, from this perspective,

145 shifts the attention from the protection of individual species and the emphasis on human benefits to the
146 importance of promoting and curating ecological interactions in which diverse species can thrive and
147 thus to larger constellations of multispecies life. Convivial conservation implies to question and
148 dismantle the modernist gaze (Krauss, 2021), for example with regard to easily naturalized human-
149 animal hierarchies and power-relations, and to encourage viable forms of species co-living, not
150 necessarily devoid of conflict but providing enough room for mutual development. Conviviality, in this
151 framework, effectively enacts a critique of essentialism in ecological thought and conservationist
152 practice; it draws attention to the affording qualities of multispecies cohabitation and the many
153 possibilities, even though often asymmetric, that emerge where species meet. This notion of conviviality
154 comes very close to presently developed understandings of the term in multispecies studies, where based
155 on Haraway's (2008) agenda-setting work conviviality is often defined in relation to the possibilities of
156 'becoming-with'. Convivial life, in this view, is above all characterized by its salient, perhaps unique,
157 capacity to *enable* co-becoming, and thus ideally results in the profusion of multispecies opportunities
158 and potentialities that depend on the ecological whole. This again suggests, in sync with other
159 scholarship on the issue, that conviviality operates on the level of emergent biocultural wholes – be it
160 systems, structures, assemblages or networks.

161 Convivialists across disciplines commonly accept the relational underpinnings of their projects
162 (e.g., Foggin et al., 2021) but, depending on their background, often face difficulties with properly
163 describing and integrating either human or nonhuman contributions. The environmental humanities and
164 some branches of environmental/animal history have so far spawned the most elaborate and considerate
165 attempts to consolidate the two (e.g., Donati, 2019; Moraru, 2015; Rigby, 2020; Van Dooren, 2019),
166 framing conviviality from the perspective of how species interfere with each other's projects to
167 commission other-affirmative change and novelty. In particular cityscapes have garnered much attention
168 within these discussions as urban spaces "have always been, to a greater or lesser extent, multispecies
169 locales" (Rigby, 2018: 73). 'Green cities' have to truly accommodate both humans and nonhumans and
170 cater to their needs; they have to seek out synergistic solutions, both material and immaterial, facilitating
171 multispecies cohabitation and the forging of opportunities *for all* city dwellers irrespectively of their
172 taxonomic status. Kate Rigby (2018) articulates this project explicitly with Val Plumwood's (2003,

173 2006) call for cultural practices of ‘deep sustainability’ which are on the constant look-out beyond the
174 human. For Bird Rose and Van Dooren (2012: 17), for example, urban multispecies conviviality consists
175 of a “being together that is not reducible to shared identities [...] but [consists of] a temporary
176 identification with others in a shared place”, where “[i]dentification,’ in contrast to ‘identity,’ does not
177 require that we share an essence or even a project, but simply that we are attentive to another’s presence,
178 to their way of being in a place.” For environmental humanists, the plasticity and adaptability of animal
179 behavior thus needs to be met with (radical) human cultural openness towards the nonhuman other, new
180 forms of multispecies sensibility and attentiveness, and, crucially, a new ethics of more-than-human
181 care. Conviviality, in this view, cannot be reduced to mere ‘matters of fact’ but conjures the urgency to
182 examine and reflect on the responsibilities of earthly co-inhabitation as ‘matters of care’ (Puig de la
183 Bellacasa, 2017).

184 As noted above, early formulations of conviviality have resonated with a more-or-less explicit
185 notion of the ‘commons’ and this legacy has recently been belabored by more-than-human approaches
186 to draw awareness to the importance of a ‘multispecies commons’ (e.g., Baynes-Rock, 2013; Bresnihan,
187 2015; Haldrup et al., 2022) in fostering conviviality-affording practices and convivial constellations of
188 life. As Hussain and Brusgaard (2023) have argued, comparative explorations of multispecies
189 commoning can be conducive to answering important questions of multispecies conviviality, for
190 example in the context of human-beaver relations, where convivial life depends on the sharing of key
191 resources within co-inhabited and co-curated landscapes. By extending the notion of the commons to a
192 multispecies world, we can perhaps arrive at a preliminary understanding of conviviality as an
193 affirmative coming together of independent agentic life build on a recognized and cultivated commons
194 that is enacted across difference (including species).

195 Conviviality in this sense can be an analytical lens to bring up the past in new ways or to re-
196 interpret the archaeological evidence at hand, but it can also be understood as an open and inviting
197 method that can be applied in the service of post-qualitative inquiry (St. Pierre, 2021). Drawing on this
198 potential and by emphasizing the concepts ethical dimension and critical potential, we in the following
199 investigate the possibilities of deploying it as an experimental archaeological method. What kind of
200 issues can be addressed by mobilizing conviviality in the context of the deep past? How may convivial

201 thinking affect our understandings and interpretations of the past? Does conviviality have the potential
202 to think about (radically) different pasts and their varied representations? And how may convivial
203 thinking change the narratives about past relationships and interdependences?

204

205 **Probing Conviviality in the Deep Past**

206 The Anthropocene moment, as a counterpoint to the human deep past, has proffered a host of novel
207 “intracorporeal encounters” between diverse human and nonhuman agents, and has come to frame a
208 range of significant “wild spaces of conviviality [] emerging in multispecies cities where improvisation,
209 risk, and accountability are all in play” (Kirksey et al., 2018: 617). Arregui (2023) has for example
210 shown how the meeting of humans and wild pigs in the suburban periphery of Barcelona decisively
211 reorients the behavior and attitudes of all of the involved agents, thereby promoting unique forms of
212 reciprocal but always precarious human-porcine co-living. The author proposes to address this emergent
213 form of species co-living as an ‘infraspecies’ relationship, as convivial coexistence unfolds not with
214 reference to supposedly stable species categories but is negotiated between *individual* humans and pigs
215 who interfere with each other’s lives in situated, often idiosyncratic and deeply ambivalent ways.
216 Arregui’s (2023) infraspecies ethnography powerfully documents that humans and pigs are drawn
217 together as peri-urban co-dwellers – facilitated by acorn-rich forest, household garbage, lawns, plenty
218 of water resources and anthropogenic feeding – and have to cultivate generative forms of mutually
219 attentive ‘indifference’ and ‘interpatience’ (Candea, 2010), allowing them to coordinate their projects
220 without substantial cutbacks or serious existential trouble. Humans and pigs exhibit habituated forms of
221 ‘relational attunement’ (Arregui, 2023: 121) and the ways they encounter, perceive and co-constitute
222 each other resists ‘fixation’ – they “reciprocally capture” one another in relations far from set’
223 (Stengers, 2011; quote from Arregui, 2023: 120). This fragile coming together of humans and pigs can
224 be described as a form of multispecies conviviality, yet configured in such a way that porcine others
225 may simultaneously appears as ‘wild’ and ‘tame’, ‘rural’ and ‘urban’ or ‘pest’ and ‘neighbor’. These
226 qualities, then, are potentials, not essentials, and they depend on the particularities and contingencies of
227 the interstices and intimacies that emerge from concrete, spatiotemporally specific human-pig
228 encounters and gatherings.

229 Human-pig relationships in the deep past can be examined in similar ways and may reveal
230 previously unrecognized patterns of convivial life. The importance of pigs in the lifeworlds and
231 ecosystems inhabited by early-to-mid Holocene people in Northern Europe, especially in Southern
232 Scandinavia, has long been recognized but the question has traditionally been cast as ‘hunting’ (wild
233 boar) vs. ‘farming’ (domestic pig). Only recently have archaeologists begun to look for evidence of
234 more subtle forms of pig management and its material and biochemical signatures. Stable isotope
235 analysis has for example revealed that *some* wild boar specimens may have consistently exploited
236 aquatic resources made available by human activity in the landscape (Maring and Riede, 2019). The
237 evidence for gradual changes in wild boar morphology documented over the course of the Mesolithic
238 taken to signal changed livelihoods in increasingly human-shaped habitats (e.g., Cucchi et al., 2023;
239 Magnell, 2006) thereby coincides with the availability of open spaces and presumably pasture close to
240 human habitations and a general shift in woodland ecologies with notably increased oak abundance in
241 the later Mesolithic (Berglund and Larsson, 1991). At the same time, the remains of pigs – especially
242 their teeth but also their mandibles – are increasingly associated with Mesolithic human burials
243 (Grünberg, 2013), and some of these items may have been curated and exchanged over considerable
244 distances (Mannermaa et al., 2019). An early Mesolithic deposit at the site of Blätterhöhle recognized
245 as intentional for example contains the skull remains of both a human and several wild boars (Orschiedt
246 et al., 2012), pointing to socially significant relationships between *some* representatives of the two
247 species. These associations may thus be interpreted as zoomaterializations of increasingly intimate, co-
248 woven human and suid lives. The underlying dynamic strongly supports conviviality: wild pigs benefit
249 from environmental changes and human-catered landscape affordances, are in turn drawn into human
250 taskscapes (sensu Ingold, 2022) and thus elicit human attention. Importantly, this configuration also
251 unlocks new hunting opportunities for humans and can thus be described as reciprocal, as both humans
252 and pigs can benefit and thrive.

253 Human-pig conviviality may be amplified when human foragers themselves develop an interest
254 in tending and expanding oak stands, for example by means of pyrotechnology, and through ‘ecologies
255 of fear’ maintained by anthropogenic activity render these habitats comparatively predator devoid. Such
256 a scenario is for example supported by contextual evidence from Jomon (Bleed and Matsui, 2010) –

257 complex hunter-gatherer societies inhabiting parts of Japan at the Pleistocene-Holocene juncture.
258 Consonant with Late Mesolithic Scandinavia, stable isotope data suggest that wild boar were encouraged
259 by human-procured aquatic resources (Matsui et al., 2002), Jomon foragers promoted clustered oak-rich
260 habitats close to settlement sites (Bleed and Matsui, 2010; Crawford, 2008, 2018) and in turn captured
261 wild boar and other animals attracted in this way. Similar dynamics may have fueled millennial-scale
262 trajectories of wild pig management in Southwest Asia (Vigne et al., 2009), supplying the synanthropic
263 basis (Baumann, 2023) for subsequent pig domestication. Brumm and colleagues (2021), in a
264 comparable vein, have discussed the prominent place of suids in the earliest Paleolithic rock art of
265 Southeast Asia in relation to the possible accrument of deep-historical forms of human-pig
266 commensalism. Such visual culture may thus reflect the generative dimension of situated systems of
267 human-nonhuman conviviality, creating multispecies intimacies and fostering habitual attunement while
268 delegating the involved beings an important place in each other's daily pursuits without curtailing their
269 development, agency, and livelihood.

270 Hussain and Brusgaard (2023) have recently suggested that the Mesolithic settlement of
271 Northern Europe was profoundly facilitated by the landscape-scale activity of beavers – what they term
272 'geopraxis' (following Schroer, 2022). The situated systems of human-beaver co-existence the authors
273 reconstruct are primarily based on human foraging dependencies on beaver-generated resource
274 affordances but also point to an important convivial element. The combination of salient hunting,
275 fowling, fishing and plant-gathering opportunities for human foragers opened up and curated by beaver
276 others (see also Coles, 2006) renders beaver neighborhoods intrinsically valuable (Hjørungdal, 2019),
277 orienting human sensibility, attentiveness and care towards the presence and world-making proficiency
278 of these animals. Human forager projects, in other words, align with some key beaver projects in the
279 landscape and beaver livelihood therefore demands affirmation. Curational hunting practices – i.e., the
280 lack of overharvesting of beavers – throughout the Mesolithic may be cited in support of this convivial
281 logic of human-beaver cohabitation. In addition, Hussain and Brusgaard (2023) draw attention to the
282 possibility that such evolved human-beaver commons are undermined and ultimately dissolved as
283 pastoralist and agriculturalist practices shift the attention to other animals and habitats and put growing

284 ecological pressure on beavers (see Liarsou, 2013, 2015, 2020 for similar arguments), so that human
285 projects begin to gradually repel beaver projects.

286 Other examples for possible forms of deep-time multispecies conviviality can be distilled from
287 the evolution of early synanthropism (Baumann, 2023; Hussain, 2023; Klegarth, 2017; O'Connor,
288 2013). Baumann and colleagues (2023) have for example shown that hunter-gatherer settlement activity
289 and surplus hunting during the earlier Gravettian of Southern Moravia consistently created valuable
290 high-caloric point resources – in some cases possibly even ‘food bonanzas’ – and in this way attracted
291 common ravens. These findings confirm earlier hypotheses formulated based on the unique
292 archaeological settlement signature and avifaunal spectrum of the relevant Gravettian sites in what is
293 today the Czech Republic (Bochenski et al., 2009; Hussain, 2019; Kost and Hussain, 2019; O'Connor,
294 2013) but enable new interpretations of the role of ravens in the respective Gravettian societies. As
295 humans emerged as highly predictable herbivore, especially mammoth, carrion accumulators and
296 simultaneously deterred other larger carnivores as signaled by the extraordinary rarity of bite or gnaw
297 marks within zooarchaeological assemblages (generally <1%; Svoboda et al., 2019; Wilczyński et al.,
298 2015, 2017; Wojtal et al., 2012, 2020), and possibly even removed them purposefully from settlement
299 and carrion sites (Wilczyński et al., 2020) and likely maintained meat and bone caches as well as waste
300 disposal areas in the vicinity (Svoboda et al., 2019), Gravettian corvids adapted to these early
301 anthropogenic micro-ecologies, were in turn demographically promoted, and became consistently
302 entangled with human lifeworlds and key foraging activities in the wider landscape. Humans, in
303 response, integrated them into their cultural and cosmological repertoire, not because of their intrinsic
304 significance but because of the relational attunement of humans and ravens and the latter’s situated
305 prominence afforded by the specific exposition and intersection of the two in the landscape. The
306 acquisition of raven feathers as an important cultural practice in this Gravettian setting (Wertz et al.,
307 2015) may then be seen not so much as a question of human ability and cognition but as a result of the
308 phenomenological imbrication and salience of ravens within the everyday pursuits and projects of
309 human foragers. The importance of raven bones in these zooarchaeological assemblages, in other words,
310 gives witness to a ‘mutual ecology’ (Fuentes, 2010) and a more-than-human neighborhood in which
311 both humans and ravens can thrive and ‘co-become’, orienting their behaviors, attentions and concerns

312 towards each other. As such, this deep-time configuration would qualify as a situated convivial form of
313 Upper Paleolithic multispecies life.

314 A similar argument can be made for some early human-fox encounters. Red foxes rank among
315 the candidate ‘early adopter’ species (O’Connor, 2013), with the capacity to quickly redress their
316 behaviors in order to make a living close to or in emerging human-shaped ecologies. Stable isotope
317 evidence obtained from Pleistocene red foxes spanning the Middle-to-Upper Paleolithic sequence in the
318 Swabian Jura in Southwestern Germany indicates that foxes systematically took advantage of human
319 foraging spoils, especially from horse and reindeer, from the Early Upper Paleolithic onwards, framing
320 a distinct human-adapted feeding niche, but that such behavior is not evident in the preceding Middle
321 Paleolithic (Baumann, 2023; Baumann et al., 2020). While most attention has been paid to the
322 implications of this pattern in terms of ecosystem impacts and the potential role of *Homo sapiens* as a
323 hyper-niche constructor, precipitating more recent Earth-system transformations, the lessons for
324 conviviality studies have so far hardly been considered. In the Eastern Mediterranean Levant, where
325 foxes are notably abundant throughout the Epipaleolithic-Neolithic sequence (Yeshurun et al., 2009)
326 and were likely promoted by increasing human site fidelity and waste accumulation, foxes or some of
327 their body parts also make an appearance in human burials (Maher et al., 2011, 2012). This is not only
328 suggestive of evolved forms of human-fox co-sociality, mediated by increasingly interwoven lifeworlds,
329 but, similar to the infraspecies human-pig relations discussed above, points to mutual habituation and
330 contingent forms of other-oriented engagement with long-term consequences for both human and fox
331 behaviors. Attending to foxes, in other words, became more than just a question of sustenance and/or
332 resource acquisition but incurred questions of meaning and care, which are central to the negotiation of
333 convivial constellations of species co-living.

334 To conclude, mobilizing the concept of conviviality opens up some promising avenues to
335 fundamentally re-imagine the deep past and the nature of human life therein. Deploying conviviality as
336 a critical lens helps to flag up and deconstruct one-sided Western framings and shifts the attention to the
337 contexts and reasons for successful, millennial-scale species cohabitation. What comes into view, in this
338 way, is a dynamic of behavioral cross-adjustment and co-orientation that changes the course of
339 evolutionary and historical developments alike. The strength of this perspective lies in the potential to

340 work out what forms of conviviality become possible and under which circumstances, and how and
341 when they fail. Not every interspecies relationship is a testimony of convivial life, of course, and paleo-
342 conviviality studies may therefore isolate important pitfalls for how to live together with other animals
343 without collapsing their potential to thrive and act on their own terms. These insights can be crucial,
344 even if often basic, for envisioning truly multispecies futures and novel convivial approaches to nature
345 conservation. In the following section, we explore the implications of this potential of a convivial
346 perspective for museum narratives and other heritage practices.

347

348 **Presenting Conviviality: Archaeological Museum Narratives**

349 Adam Dodd and colleagues (2013: 1) have pointed out that museums – as institutions that frame and
350 address important societal problems and engage visitors to critically discuss them – should also
351 responsibly approach the increasingly paramount subject of nonhuman animals and their place in human
352 history, because the way the subject is exhibited, greatly affects and shapes our current and future
353 interactions with animal others. Dodd *et al.* (2013) identify two main motivations for presenting and
354 centering nonhuman animals and environmental contexts in museums: 1) to evoke appreciation to the
355 rich and diverse worlds of nonhuman animals and 2) to provoke reflection on how cruel and destructive
356 humans often act towards them today. These two motivations are rooted in a critical reading of late-
357 capitalist attitudes towards animals (e.g., McMullen, 2015; Stache, 2020; Taylor and Twine, 2014),
358 especially the ways in which they have been marginalized and often treated merely as resources or
359 commodities in industrial production chains (but see Mc Loughlin, 2022 for the involved complexities).
360 Conviviality, originally formulated as a critique of degrading effects of capitalism, supports this way of
361 thinking about nonhuman animals on display and to draw attention to the capitalist ‘alienation’ from
362 animals as nature (Cassegård, 2021; Stache, 2020) as well as the resulting rifts separating human and
363 animal lives, lifeworlds and sensibilities. Archaeological museums can re-contextualize this diagnosis
364 with knowledge on human-animal relationships in deep history and conviviality thinking supplies a
365 powerful lens of doing so.

366 Archaeological museums might be then important starting points for renewed discussions on
367 conviviality and multispecies co-living, and can so join and supplement cross-cultural (e.g., Schroer,

368 2021; Whitehouse, 2015) and Indigenous perspectives (e.g., Kimmerer, 2021) on how to imagine and
369 forge a different future. Although archaeological museums traditionally showcase diverse
370 zoomaterialities and varied exhibits referencing past human-animal relationships, they have tended to
371 solidify the human-centered narratives and clichés that boil down to framing animals as resources, as
372 illustrating the human domestication and conquest of nature, and only very rarely as companions, co-
373 actors or valued significant others in past worlds (but see Mulville, 2019). Stobiecka (2023) has argued
374 that archaeological museums have the immense potential here to probe new theories and approaches and
375 help to overcome such one-sided and increasingly problematic narratives and to host critical and more
376 engaged displays. This call to substantially re-configure more traditional approaches in the museum
377 space, focusing less on practical concerns (such as conservation, documentation, maintenance of
378 collections and digitization: see e.g. Skeates, 2017) and more on engaging visitors with problems,
379 debates, crises and challenges currently high on the socio-political agenda (Harrison and Sterling, 2020;
380 Hussain and Riede, 2020; Sterling, 2020; Stevenson, 2022; Stobiecka, 2022b), is also supported by the
381 re-definition of the museum put forward by the International Council of Museums (ICOM) in 2022.
382 Museums of today need to be inclusive hubs that foster diversity and sustainability and spark critical
383 discourse as how to achieve these aims. Museums are increasingly seen as ‘contact zones’ (Clifford,
384 1997), providing a social space and ‘testbed’ for dialogue and negotiation. As such, museums need to
385 respond not just to ‘matters of fact’ but speak to ‘matters of concern’ (Latour, 2004), indeed aspire to
386 become ‘disruptive’ voices of the latter (Fenske and Elpers, 2020). Calling on Bewes’ (2010) post-
387 critical stance, museums should attend to their time ‘not against the grain’ but ‘with it’. Given this role,
388 museums, and particularly archaeological museums, could be key sites of creative, provocative and
389 engaged convivial thinking.

390 Against this background, an exploration of how multispecies conviviality of the deep past is
391 belabored in archaeological museums is useful and helps to identify current constrictions and potentials.
392 While arguing that museums have the potential to participate in critical theory-work in archaeology and
393 beyond (Stobiecka, 2023: 6), we probe into two archaeological exhibitions with conviviality purchase
394 to exemplify and reframe museum spaces as agents of debating, practicing and learning about alternative
395 forms of interspecies cohabitation: the permanent exhibition of Lascaux IV – Centre International de

396 l'Art Pariétal in Montignac-Lascaux and the *Age of Animals*, a part of the permanent display in the Stone
397 Age gallery of the Neues Museum in Berlin.

398 The fourth retelling of the Lascaux story is an inspiring example of a critical approach towards
399 human and nonhuman animal narratives in the archaeological museum landscape, illustrating how
400 understandings of conviviality may materialize in exhibitions. The new center for the interpretation of
401 the famous cave paintings of Lascaux opened in 2019 and encourages visitors to participate in guided
402 tours, individual attendance being limited to those who pre-book a 'contemplative visit' (*visite*
403 *contemplation*). The exhibition comprises interactive multimedia (videos, digital tablets), the complete
404 1:1 reconstruction of the cave of Lascaux including its world-renowned Upper Paleolithic parietal
405 imagery as well as smaller reconstructions and 3D models of the cave and selected paintings.

406 The permanent exhibition of Lascaux IV starts with a short movie outlining in detail the
407 environmental conditions surroundings of the cave during the Upper Paleolithic. Already in this movie,
408 the museum deploys a different range of interpretative lenses than most traditional archaeological
409 museums (or museums of natural history). The animation illustrating past climate conditions, landscape
410 organizations and wild animal species populating the latter (e.g., bison, bear, deer, horse) purposefully
411 decentralizes the human and the image of the 'hunter', which typically prevails in more conservative
412 takes. Past humans appear as one of many species; they are not the *clou* of the story, neither are they
413 separated out from nature. This framing is reinforced by the guides' commentary, stressing the animality
414 of Upper Paleolithic people, the on-par status of other animals (also in quantitative terms), and the
415 embeddedness of humans into their ecologies. Following the movie, visitors are invited to explore the
416 cave reconstruction. Again, the presented narrative does not focus so much on the exceptionality of
417 people – the 'human genius' – mastering the painting techniques and creating the naturalistic drawings,
418 but places Lascaux's cave art into a holistic ecology. Similar to the study of early rock art in Oceania by
419 Brumm and colleagues (2021), Lascaux IV positions animal-themed visual culture as a reflection of a
420 natural world dominated by nonhuman animals, and so as a cultural expression of human-nonhuman
421 cohabitation and multispecies attunement. During a guided tour one of us participated in 2020, the guide
422 specifically emphasized that the realism and behavioral details of the depicted animals are inconsistent
423 with an extractive-exploitative ideology, instead testifying to human-animal intimacy and co-sociality.

424 The storylining therefore defies the modernist gaze (Krauss, 2021) and challenges typical Western and
425 human-centered narratives, despite archaeologists and museums continuing to rally around the notion
426 that Upper Paleolithic cave art primarily reflects the dawn of human ‘symbolic cognition’ (e.g., Cook,
427 2013), the mythologization of nature, and religious thought (Clottes, 2011, 2016).

428 Lascaux IV perpetuates an environmental story of the deep past in which human and animal
429 lives are interlaced, both actors meaningfully and generatively cohabit the landscape, and have the
430 potential to negotiate relationships to enter into alliances (e.g., human-bovine, human-horse) or devise
431 antagonisms (e.g., horse-bear, human-bear). The intention seems not to present the distant past as an
432 ‘Eden-like’ place, but to explore the various possibilities of populating the past by different species. Yet
433 – while this accentuation of the potentiality of species co-living, especially in terms of human affect,
434 cognition and cultural practices, clearly resonates with convivial concerns, there is also the tendency to
435 fall back into questionable, and chiefly Western polarities. During the guided tour,
436 it is for example highlighted that ‘unlike today, the deep past was not the time when humans were
437 dangerous to other animals’ and ‘these humans were not dominating nature’. Although upsetting human-
438 centered narrative of the domination, exploitation and subjugation of nature and speaking to challenges
439 of current climate change and the effects of late capitalism, Upper Paleolithic people tend to be
440 ‘naturalized’, reintroducing tropes of primitivism and nature romanticism.

441 Visitors are confronted with a mirror of the Anthropocene – an imagination of its antithesis –
442 rather than constructive pointers, as we cannot simply unroll our lives back to the Paleolithic. The deep
443 past is portrayed as a period of minimal human ecological interference, and nature, as a result, tends to
444 be cast as ‘wilderness’ – an idea deeply entwined with Western colonialism (e.g., Cronon, 1996; Nash,
445 1973). The conviviality lens offers a way out of this dilemma, as it can help to escape the bindings of
446 colonialism, progressivism and the Anthropocene by shifting the attention to the conditions,
447 consequences and drawbacks of situated multispecies life, without reproducing misleading narratives of
448 the past as conflict, harmony or domination and resolving the tension between natural and cultural
449 history without the necessity to pitch an origin story – a pseudo-mythology of Western modernity. In
450 this way, the deep past can become a fruitful arena for post-critical museums to initiate a dialogue about
451 what forms of multispecies life are humanly possible, thus sidelining melancholy of what is lost. By

452 foregrounding possibility and more-than-human potential, this can also supply a timely antidote to the
453 kinds of climate and environmental determinism plaguing Paleolithic studies (Livingstone, 2012) and
454 to instead foster ecological possibilism and hope.

455 The *Age of Animals* display in the Stone Age gallery of the Neues Museum in Berlin, one of the
456 ‘über-museums’ (Swain, 2007), confidently starts with the self-declared need to re-think human-nature
457 relations in the prehistoric past. The exhibition attempts to re-frame the much-discussed transition from
458 hunter-gatherer to agricultural and livestock-based lifeways from a more-than-human perspective. The
459 story is told through three evocative dioramas, presenting the skeletal remains of key nonhuman animals
460 against a black background filled with drawings of the daily life of the involved Stone Age human
461 communities. The socket of each diorama holds diagnostic artefacts (knapped, polished and ground
462 stone, pottery, etc.), corresponding timelines, as well as short introductory texts touching upon the role
463 of animals, the development of human technologies and changing ways of living in the past. The mode
464 of presentation, including the materiality of the display and the aesthetic framing, place the attention
465 firmly on the animals and so decenter prehistoric people. The elk so emerges as a co-protagonist of the
466 Final Paleolithic/Mesolithic, while the goat takes over an important role in the subsequent Neolithic –
467 thus gauging the contours of a deep animal prehistory (Hussain, 2023). Waivering troublesome life-
468 sized mannequins of humans in stereotyped gender roles, textual and visual elements emphasize the
469 animals’ role in shaping past realities, without reducing them to human tokens to be ‘used’ or ‘thought
470 with’. They instead come into view as ‘good to live with’ (sensu Kirksey and Helmreich, 2010; van
471 Dooren et al., 2016). A convivialist lens would help to bring the diversity of past human-animal
472 relationships into even clearer focus and to not only critique the long-standing anthropocentrism of
473 picturing human deep history, but instead to bring them up as educational frames to reimagine how we
474 relate to nonhuman worlds (and these worlds relate to us), conjuring up matters of care and attentiveness,
475 to think with concepts of *entanglement* and *assemblage* as a humanist method to work towards a better
476 future (St. Pierre, 2021).

477 As heuristic ‘spaces of reflection’ (Gesing et al., 2019), archaeological museums have thus the
478 opportunity to eclipse past-present oppositions; by re-enacting, disassembling and re-composing
479 ‘naturecultures’, they can play a role in exploring innovative approaches to analyze and imagine the co-

480 presence of humans and nonhumans, to posit that ‘we have never been modern’ (Latour, 1993), to
481 showcase the inseparability and inherent mutuality of human and nonhuman lives, and to pivot the
482 responsibilities and accountabilities of human societies. They can assist in forging a new archaeological
483 imagination that recognizes the contested nature of the past (Lowenthal, 2015; see also Shanks, 2012)
484 and engages with what could perhaps be called our shared ‘convivial heritage’. We argue it is an
485 important mission of the Anthropocene museum to compel conversations as to the prerequisites,
486 complexities, successes and failures of planetary life and cohabitation, and to call upon the human
487 capacity to re-invent ourselves in the face of critical challenges and concerns (Feige, 2022). Conviviality
488 can serve as a kaleidoscope and inflection point of such matters of concern, while simultaneously
489 reverberating, as we have shown, with current approaches of addressing the deep past in the museum.
490 Attending to convivial heritage allows to take advantage of the empiricism of Paleolithic and Mesolithic
491 research and their insights on human-animal intersections (see above), and to bring them to bear in
492 broader discussions on a new ethics of care, a just multispecies future, and a more hospitable planet, and
493 so to critically, constructively, and imaginatively engage with the unfolding Anthropocene polycrisis.
494 As such, conviviality offers a potent optic to belabor the past and present to attend to a ‘damaged’ planet
495 (Tsing, 2021) and to re-imagine the place and role of the human on it – key responsibilities of the vision
496 of an inclusive, future-making post-critical and post-qualitative archaeological museum.

497 A truly convivial museum should thereby render conviviality tangible – to support authentic
498 *convivial experience* – and as such become a multispecies hotspot. The convivial museum so comes into
499 view as a space where gatherings of diverse species are encouraged, lived, enacted and/or simulated and
500 where convivial forms of life are enabled, probed, tested, and experimented with – a generative more-
501 than-human space itself. The convivial museum could be a testbed for a ‘democracy of species’
502 (Kimmerer, 2021), a hopeful utopia where humans and animals come together to jointly configure their
503 attentions, practices, lives and concerns. This, inter alia, draws attention to the importance of convivial
504 infrastructure and symbiotic architecture (Gunawan, 2015; Lucas, 2018), to the spatial and architectural
505 layout of the museum as a space, but also to the role of human infrastructural projects of the past and
506 present as conceptual bridges to center and engage with issues of species coexistence (Tsing et al., 2020),
507 as also increasingly illustrated by hunter-gatherer archaeologies (Anderson et al., 2017). Archaeological

508 sites can in this way equally become important touchstones of interspecies attentiveness, integrated into
509 museum spaces or not.

510 Archaeological sites are themselves multispecies hotspots in the present as their varied
511 multispecies affordances orient human and animal behaviors towards each other, and can so catalyze
512 fresh perspectives and conversations on conviviality. As Stobiecka (2022a) has explored in some detail,
513 archaeological sites constitute lively heritage, notwithstanding an elongated history of sterilizing
514 archaeological sites (Olsen et al., 2012: 50-53) as remnants of a long gone, essentially dead past. Again,
515 this history only testifies to a misleading past-present opposition and overlooks the active and
516 transformative potential of past materialities in the present. While “ancient, heritage ruins are often
517 presented to us neatly, for our occasional enjoyment” (Olsen and Pétursdóttir, 2016: 38; see also Shanks,
518 1998) and as representations of elapsed *human* projects, the brute fact that life strives to co-opt such
519 sites as ‘spandrels’ of new behaviors (Gould and Lewontin, 1997) and so constantly re-inscribes itself
520 into the material legacies of the past is easily overlooked. Archaeological sites can so delineate “contact
521 zones where lines separating nature from culture have broken down, where encounters between *Homo*
522 *sapiens* and other beings generate mutual ecologies and coproduced niches” (Rigby, 2018: 76-77).
523 Archaeological sites, traditionally conceived as credentials of past human ingenuity and exceptionality,
524 may thus, ironically, help ‘thinking with’ other species and so be conducive for convivial thinking. The
525 integration of the ancient Greek landscape of Agrigento in Sicily (Badami, 2021; Stobiecka, 2022a) into
526 larger ecological conservation programs illustrates this transformative potential, exposing “levels of
527 power, compulsion, and programming” (Illich, 2009 [1973]: 25) and challenging the modern tourist
528 gaze (Urry, 2011). Defusing notions of archaeological sites as denuded of life and livelihoods and
529 instead presenting them as nurturing multispecies hospitality can then help to reposition heritage sites
530 in times of crisis.

531

532 **Conclusions: Archaeology of Conviviality in Theory and Practice**

533 This paper has offered conviviality 1) as a method to re-examine past human-animal relationships and
534 challenge their traditional representations and 2) as a critically engaged lens to spark creative dialogue
535 on multispecies co-living, responsible attentiveness to the nonhuman other in securing local and

536 planetary livelihoods, and radical re-imaginings of the possibilities for species co-existence in the near
537 and long-term future. By harnessing, deploying, and encouraging conviviality thinking, archaeology can
538 make a substantial contribution to today's existential challenges and concerns in society and
539 environment. Playing to its empirical strengths and the need to continuously re-articulate past, present
540 and future horizons of significance, and to probe what the field has to say in times of total crisis,
541 archaeology can so join other voices in the academy and beyond to provide fresh perspectives on the
542 diversity of species cohabitation, its conditions, consequences, and limitations as well as its material,
543 cultural and cognitive imports. Archaeological perspectives, alternative readings, and re-readings of an
544 always contested past in this way promise to complement nature conservation efforts in the present, as
545 convivial analyses expose the fundamental inseparability of human and nonhuman lives and livelihoods,
546 highlighting the importance of considering human behavior and material infrastructures in nature
547 conservation and ecological restoration programs. Mapping out and comparing convivial forms of life
548 as they unfold in different deep-historical contexts and at the intersection of different species can thereby
549 add to emerging Indigenous and anthropological perspectives on ecosystem stewardship (Hoffman et
550 al., 2021; Solange Bandiaky-Badji et al., 2023) and complement calls for 'applied zooarchaeology'
551 (Lyman, 2012; Wolverton et al., 2016), 'archaeoecology' (Crabtree and Dunne, 2022), and
552 archaeological extinction and biodiversity studies (Andermann et al., 2020; Rick and Sandweiss, 2020).
553 Thinking through the past and deep past in terms of conviviality may also provide context for broader
554 histories of zoonotic disease and so resituate phenomena such as the COVID-19 pandemic in big history.
555 We have argued that conviviality thinking can thus help to realign archaeological discourse with broader
556 societal and political preoccupations of our time and to move beyond critique – to not simply read the
557 past 'against the grain' but 'with it', and in a transformative spirit of 'slow hope' (Mauch, 2019).

558 A concern with conviviality and convivial forms of life can also change how we think about
559 archaeological museums, heritage, and orient the sensibilities and responsibilities of archaeology in the
560 Anthropocene. We have argued that conviviality can motivate and catalyze new forms of creative
561 engagement with the past in the context of a post-critical, mission-conscious museum and beyond the
562 epistemological and conceptual stereotyping that has scourged archaeology for too long. Conviviality
563 offers the opportunity to reposition archaeological knowledge as crucial for understanding the

564 fundamental interwovenness of nature and culture and inescapable interpenetration of human and
565 nonhuman behaviors and lives from local to planetary scales. As a method in museum settings,
566 conviviality as aids to overcome the tyranny of the text and to foreground the relations between narration
567 and materiality (Stobiecka, 2023); it thereby embraces a symmetrical approach (Olsen, 2012, 2013;
568 Olsen et al., 2012), recognizes the museum as creative assemblage (Pfefferkorn, 2024), and is committed
569 to multimodal storytelling. Attending to conviviality affords to forge new visions of how we as humans
570 want to inhabit this planet in the future, raise awareness of the co-dependency of humans and other
571 forms of life, and foster dialogue and learning as to the accountability and ethical obligations of humans
572 in the Anthropocene. Doing so entails to de-center humans and their projects in representations of the
573 past, and ultimately to overcome representationalist approaches altogether, as interactive deep pasts
574 emphasizing diversity in autonomy that can inspire hopeful futures and repairing a damaged planet are
575 brought to the fore. Commonly understood as human-exclusive spaces, archaeological museums
576 themselves then need to be re-imagined and as multispecies hotspot may hold hitherto overlooked
577 potential as a transformative ‘mangle of practice’ (sensu Pickering, 2009). As Flexner (2020) argues,
578 ethical consideration of conviviality may even transform archaeological practices themselves and so
579 contribute to de-growth and alternative forms of ecocultural governance and biopolitics.

580

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583

584 **Author contributions**

585 STH and MS contributed equally to the research presented in this paper.

586

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